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LEGAL BASIS AND INTERACTIVE SERVICES OF THE NATIONAL GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN

Abstract. *The article contains some comments on the reforms implemented in the field of informatization in our country, investments in information and communication technologies (ICT) in the state economic sector, the widespread introduction of geographic information systems (GIS), one of the ICT sectors, online geoinformation services of GIS and their development.*

Key words: *information and communication technologies, national geographic information systems, online geoinformation services, cartography, ecology, seismology, spatial data.*

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O‘ZBEKISTON MILLIY GEOGRAFIK AXBOROT TIZIMINING QONUNIY ASOSLARI VA INTERAKTIV XIZMATLARI

Annotatsiya. Maqolada mamlakatimizda axborotlashtirish sohasida amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar, davlat iqtisodiy sektorida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari (AKT)ga jalb etilgan investitsiyalar, AKT sohalaridan biri geografik axborot tizimlari (GAT)ning keng joriy etilishi, GATning onlayn geoaxborot xizmatlari va ularni rivojlantirish xususida ba’zi mulohazalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari (AKT), milliy geografik axborot tizimlari (MGAT), onlayn geoaxborot xizmatlari, kartografiya, ekologiya, seysmologiya, fazoviy ma’lumotlar

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ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬНЫЕ ОСНОВЫ И ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫЕ УЛУГИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ГЕОГРАФИЧЕСКОЙ ИНФОРМАЦИОННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

Аннотация. В статье описаны реформы, проводимые в сфере информатизации в нашей стране, инвестиции в информационно-коммуникационные технологии (ИКТ) в государственном секторе экономики, широкое внедрение геоинформационных систем (ГИС) как одного из секторов ИКТ, онлайн геоинформационные службы ГАТ и их развитие, даны комментарии.

Ключевые слова: информационно-коммуникационные технологии (ИКТ), национальные географические информационные системы (ГИС), геоинформационные онлайн-сервисы, картография, экология, сейсмология, пространственные данные.

Introduction

As a result of the consistent implementation of reforms in the field of informatization, the development of modern information and communication technologies (ICT) and telecommunication systems and their widespread implementation are being achieved based on the tasks set before all sectors and state administration bodies of the republic [1].

Incorporation of information technologies into public administration, studies conducted by experts in more than 60 countries have shown that ICT is closely related to economic growth only in developed countries, that is, in developing countries, the impact of ICT is small, it is noted that only after reaching of its development a certain extent it is possible to ensure the growth of the gross domestic product per capita.

The amount of investments involved in ICT in the economic sector of the republic, and the amount of net profit of state administration bodies and enterprises analyzed over the last years can be a proof of our opinion. International experience shows that the use of ICT in public administration makes it possible to increase productivity by an average of 20% due to the reduction of time for interaction, processing and searching of information.

In the implementation of state reforms, information technologies are being actively adopted and widely introduced in economic management and government bodies. On the basis of large-scale reforms carried out in our country during the years of independence, the rapid development of ICT has a significant impact on the Republic of Uzbekistan's rightful place in the global information community. The observations show that the state is using all its capabilities to develop ICT. At the same time, the introduction of ICT into public administration began. Development of geographic information systems (hereinafter referred to as GIS) is one of the most urgent tasks in the field of ICT. GIS technologies are used in construction, cartography, ecology, seismology and many other fields [2].

The creation of a national geographic information system in Uzbekistan means the development and creation of the National Geographic Information System (NGIS) of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the rational use and protection of natural resources, the development of management decisions on the comprehensive development of regions, economic sectors and the social sphere, and to support this [3].

Implementation Method

NGIS is a functional automated complex information system that will be implemented in the entire territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, covering information on the main economic sectors and areas of activity and including the following:

- spatial information in the form of computer representation;
- a set of functional capabilities according to tasks, in which operations of geoinformation technologies are carried out.

The establishment of republican (central) and 14 regional information-analysis centers of NGIS, as well as regional centers of republican state administration and local state authorities, began.

This national system was created on the basis of the following normative documents:

- Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 27, 2013 No. PP-1989 "On measures to further develop the National Information and Communication System of the Republic of Uzbekistan" (Appendix 2, Item 5);
- Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 25, 2013 No. PQ-2045 "About the measures for the implementation of the investment project to create a national geographic information system";
- Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6079 of 05.10.2020 "DIGITAL UZBEKISTAN - 2030" STRATEGY;
- Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-5349 dated February 19, 2018 "On further improvement of information technological and communication infrastructure";
- Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 23, 2021 "On Spatial Data" No. ORQ-702.

There are the following conditions for creating NGIS:

- rapid development of information and communication technologies in the republic;
- existence of the necessary legislation and regulatory framework in the field of information and communication technologies, geoinformatics, geodesy, cartography and cadastre;
- existence of an organizational structure: the main central organization is the National Center of Geodesy and Cartography (NCGC), Geoinfocadastral SUE, regional cadastral services and registration offices.

The National Geographic Information System (NGIS) represents a complex of information resources integrated into a single system, created by ministries and agencies based on their authorities and distribution of authorities by sectors (Fig. 1).

NGIS is a multi-user system open to both professional and educational use, as well as public use [4]. In NGIS, layers are created once, modified as needed, and reused many times. NGIS may have a total of several hundred thematic layers created by competent ministries and agencies of various directions. NGIS data is in the form of layers and it mainly contains background data and other thematic data.

Basic information includes land cadastre, real estate objects, transport network, water level, boundaries, geodetic base, relief, aerial photographs [5].

Other thematic information includes flood zones, demography, energy system, water networks, wastewater networks, gas and oil pipelines.

NGIS represents a set of databases reflecting one or another state of the process inextricably linked to a single topographic-geodesic basis, and it allows to do the following:

- complex and clear presentation of information;
- accurate spatial connection and systematization of information;
- the ability to dynamically reflect and model processes and events, drawing conclusions;
- preparation of optimal management decisions in combination with programs of economic and statistical analysis.

Figure 1. Main components of NGIS.

Expected results of project implementation (Figure 2):

- Creation of the National Geographical Information System, which allows raising the level of awareness of state authorities and ensures the validity of management decisions.
- New state satellite geodetic network, which provides conditions for quick and high-accuracy location determination of various objects, including current information collection for NGIS.
- The unified computerized system of real estate cadastre and its registration provides the possibility of providing interactive public services under the "one-stop" system.
- It is an up-to-date digital cartographic base on scales from 1:200 000 to 1:2000, designed to provide information to the economy, science and defense sectors.

NGIS provides an opportunity to analyze and evaluate relevant and correct cartographic and other information in real time for the purpose of developing management decisions on the rational use of natural resources and their protection, comprehensive development of regions, economic sectors and the social sphere, and to support this. A number of standards and normative documents are also required to be developed for the creation and operation of NGIS.

Figure 2. Creating a national cartographic framework is a basic component.

Conclusion

Online geoinformation services of GIS are widely used today. An online geospatial system, also known as a web geospatial system, is a service that delivers your data to users outside of your organization. It is very important for national geodetic and cartographic organizations, geoinformatics centers, land resources committee or organizations dealing with spatial data to implement this type of service. In this case, any geospatial software you are working with will be available online. Most importantly, online services should be easy to use for the average user, and the search for information and making inquiries should be simplified.

But some geoscientists can make it look a little more complicated. Through these methods, online services can expand the scope of paid services and achieve stability. Another important aspect is that nowadays the Internet is accessed not only from personal computers, but also through mobile phones and tablets. This requires the development of special programs suitable for those devices.

Nowadays, the cost of connecting to the Internet is getting cheaper, and the speed is increasing. This development makes it possible to work online in geoinformation system programs. Therefore, we can say that online geoinformation services will achieve great success in the future.

Web-GIS is also improving. In simpler terms, Web GIS is the ability to retrieve GIS data from web pages online and perform various operations such as GIS special programs of some web pages. There are several advantages of displaying GIS through such an internet. Including:

- Worldwide access to information means the Internet is ready for use anywhere in the world.

- Standard interface: each web page has an easy-to-use browse feature and does not require any additional software or system installation (typically, a specific GIS program will need to be installed to work). This eliminates redundancy.

- Speed and cost-effectiveness: all information is available directly from the real source.

By now, taking into account the above advantages, performing GIS operations through the website is becoming the standard platform of GIS. Currently, there is a huge amount of information services on the Internet. It is permissible to include ArcIMS, GeoMedia and other programs in the list of web programs created by companies that produce GIS.

If this development continues, in the future almost all users will switch to the web GIS system. Such users may be able to view simple GIS operations or GIS products (map, graph, table), but such a web- GIS system does not provide enough information and opportunities for specialists who carry out large-scale GIS work in complex operations.

References:

1. Ergashev M.M., Q.M.Inoyatov, A.N.Inamov., Geoinformation systems on highways. Textbook, 2019, Namangan.
2. Kasimov O.K., & Rajapova S.S. (2020). Prospects for the introduction of new technologies for the development of the transport system of the republic of Uzbekistan. *Economy and society*, (6), 710-715. <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=44002983>
3. Khakimov, S., Rajapova, S., Amirkulov, F., & Islomov, E. (2021, December). Road Intersection Improvement–Main Step for Emission Reduction and Fuel Economy. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 939, No. 1, p. 012026). IOP Publishing.
4. [Intelligence of transport services is a priority of system efficiency](https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/intelligence-of-transport-services-is-a-priority-of-system-efficiency/viewer), S.S. Rajapova: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2021, <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/intelligence-of-transport-services-is-a-priority-of-system-efficiency/viewer>.
5. Rajapova S.S., Shakirova A., Automation of intelligent functions on passenger automobile transport., *Economy and society*, [3-2 \(82\)](https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=45784479), 2021, p-s. 258-262, <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=45784479>

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Хурматли ҳамкасабалар “Al-Ferganus” нашриёти ва “Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali” электрон журнали Ўзбекистон таълим хизматлари бозорида ўзининг фаолиятини бошлаганлигини маълум қиламиз.

Ажойиб имкониятдан сиз биринчилар қаторида фойдаланиб илмий нашрларингизни чоп этишингиз мумкин.

“Al-Ferganus” нашриётимиз томонидан Сиз тақдим этган дарслик, ўқув қўлланма, монография ва илмий рисоаларга ISBN, Doi халқаро рақамли идентификаторларни бириктириш, уларнинг электрон замонавий андозадаги муқовалар ва ишланмаларнинг электрон макетини яратиш, нашриётда эълон қилинган ишларни электрон ахборот нашрларида жойлаштириш хизматлари кўрсатилади.

Бизнинг нашриётимизнинг бошқа нашриётлардан фарқи шундаки, тезкор ва сифатли хизмат кўрсатамиз ҳамда энг асосийси биз Сизнинг ишларингизни Алишер Навоий номидаги Ўзбекистон Миллий кутубхонаси ва Россия Миллий кутубхонаси фондларига бепул жойлашга шунингдек, Россия илмий иқтибослик индекси (РИНЦ ва E – library) платформасига, CrossRef базаларига шартнома асосида жойлаштиришга кўмаклашамиз.

“Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali” ISSN 2181-2357 электрон журнали ҳам ўз фаолиятини бошламоқда. Бизнинг журналда Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий аттестация комиссиясининг куйидаги ихтисосликлари физика-математика, кимё, биология, геология-минералогия, техника, қишлоқ хўжалиги,

тарих, иқтисодиёт, фалсафа, филология, география, юридик, педагогика, тиббиёт санъатшунослик, архитектура, психология, социология фанлари бўйича миллий ва хорижий муаллифларнинг фанлардан эришган ютуқлари ва истиқболлари борасидаги илмий мақолалари, илмий тадқиқотлар олиб бораётган олимларнинг илмий изланишлари натижалари эълон қилинади. Электрон журнал ҳар ойда бир марта эълон қилинади.

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политехника институти.
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Kurpayanidi K.I.,

Issues of innovation and
innovation management in
the context of economic
transformation: monograph
/ Kurpayanidi K.I.,
edited by M.A.Ikramov. –
Fergana polytechnic
institute. AL-FERGANUS,
2022. – 280 p.
ISBN 978-9943-8579-2-6

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**Курпаяниди К.И.,
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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7060384>

Курпаяниди К. И., Илёсов А.А. Саноат маҳсулотлари экспортнинг ташкилий-иқтисодий механизmlарини такомиллаштириш (Фарғона вилояти саноат тармоғи мисолида): монография / Курпаяниди К. И., Илёсов А.А.; М. А. Икрамов тахрир остида. - Фарғона политехника институти. AL-FERGANUS, 2022. – 184 б. ISBN 978-9943-7707-5-1

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6618980>

Мамуров Э.Т., Гафуров А.М. CAD/CAM/CAE тизимларида лойихалаш асослари. Дарслик /Э.Т.Мамуров, А.М.Гафуров – Фарғона: AL-FERGANUS, 2022.- 200 б.

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Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий ва ўрта махсус таълим вазирлиги ҳузуридаги Олий, ўрта махсус ва профессионал таълим йўналишлари бўйича ўқув-услубий бирлашмалар фаолиятини мувофиқлаштирувчи кенгаш томонидан дарслик сифатида тавсия этилган. (2022 йил 9 сентябр №302-сонли буйруқ).

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Mamurov E.T., Xusanov Yu.Yu., Yusupov S.M. Mexatronika asoslari. Darslik/ - E.T.Mamurov, Yu.Yu.Xusanov, S.M.Yusupov - Farg'ona: AL-FERGANUS, 2022. 280 b.
ISBN 978-9943-7707-1-3

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy, o'rta maxsus va professional ta'lim yo'nalishlari bo'yicha o'quv-uslubiy birlashmalar faoliyatini Muvofiqlashtiruvchi kengash tomonidan darslik sifatida tavsiya etilgan. (2022 yil 9 sentyabr №302-sonli buyruq).

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Mamurov E.T., Yusupov S.M., Xusanov Yu.Yu. Yo'nalishga kirish. Darslik / E.T.Mamurov, S.M.Yusupov, Yu.Yu.Xusanov - Farg'ona: AL-FERGANUS, 2022.- 150 b.
ISBN 978-9943-7707-0-6

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D.E.; edited by
M.A.Ikramov. - Fergana
polytechnic institute. AL-
FERGANUS, 2022. – 200 p.
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К.Р.Хонкелдиева.-
Фарғона политехника
институти. Фарғона: AL-
FERGANUS, 2022.-166 б.
ISBN: 978-9943-7707-7-5

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6759902>

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Рахмоназаров П.Й.
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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6750455>

Ashurov, M. S. Sanoat korxonalarida risklarni boshqarish mexanizmini takomillashtirish strategiyalari. Monografiya. Farg'ona: Al-Ferganus, 2022.- 120 b.

Ashurov Maxammadjon Sotvoldievich

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**Abdullaev A.M.,
Kurpayanidi K. I.,
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Institutional transformation
of the business sector.
Monograph. Fergana "AL-
FERGANUS", 2021. - 180
p.
ISBN: 978-9943-7189-9-
9

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M.S. Ashurov,
K.I. Kurpayanidi

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**Ashurov, M.S.,
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Problems and solutions for
the formation of a
competitive national
innovation system.
Monograph. Edited by
Doctor of Economics,
Professor Ikramov M.A.,
Fergana: Al-Ferganus,
2021.- 102 p.
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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5676027>

ASHUROV M.S., SHAKIROVA Yu. S.

EKOLOGIK MUAMMOLAR VA ULARNI HAL
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STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI

Monografiya

Farg'ona - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

Ashurov M.S., Shakirova Yu.S. Environmental problems and strategic directions of environmental management in their solution. Monograph. Edited by Doctor of Economics, Professor Ikramov M.A., Fergana: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 160 p.
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Н.Қ. Жўраева

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Жўраева, Н.Қ. Уй-жой коммунал соҳаси фаолиятини бошқариш механизмларини такомиллаштириш. Монография. - Фарғона: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 140 б.
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Mirzaev, A.T.
Methodological aspects of tourism and recreational activity management in Uzbekistan: changes and prospects: Monograph /Mirzaev A.T.; ed G. Sh. Khankeldiyeva - Fergana: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 174 p. ISBN: 978-9943-7706-3-8

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5722700>

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ВА РИВОЖЛАНИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ

Монография

Фаргона - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

Muminova, E.A.
Innovative paradigm of corporate governance at textile enterprises: methodology, experience and development prospects: monograph /Muminova E.A.; ed. G. Sh. Khankeldiyeva - Fergana: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 160 p. ISBN: 978-9943-7706-1-4

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5676091>

Набиева, Н.М. Хизмат кўрсатиш корхоналарини ривожлантиришнинг маркетинг стратегиясини ишлаб чиқиш. Монография. - Фарғона: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 162 б. ISBN: 978-9943-7189-7-5

Н.М. Набиева
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Монография

Фарғона - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5230368>

Nazarmatov, O.S. Improving the methodology of management of innovative processes in the enterprises of the textile industry. Monograph. - Fergana: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 200 p. ISBN: 978-9943-7706-2-1

О.С.Назарматов

ТЎҚИМАЧИЛИК САНОАТИ КОРХОНАЛАРИДА
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o'tkazishning maqbul
me'yor va muddatlari.
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professor F.J. Teshayev
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